

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN POST TRAUMATIC STRESS DISORDER AMONG MOTOR VEHICLE SURVIVORS AND ORTHOPAEDICS TRAUMA PATIENTS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15560551>

Received	Revised	Accepted	Published
06 April, 2025	06 May, 2025	22 May, 2025	31 May, 2025

ABSTRACT

This study investigated differences in post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) symptoms between motor vehicle accident survivors and orthopedic trauma patients, as well as between male and female patients. A total sample of 200 individuals (100 males and 100 females) was recruited from Nishtar Hospital, Multan, and DHQ Hospital, Muzaffargarh. The Post-Traumatic Stress Scale was employed to assess PTSD symptoms, and a cross-sectional research design was utilized. Data were analyzed using SPSS. The results indicated no significant difference in PTSD symptoms between motor vehicle accident survivors and orthopedic trauma patients. Similarly, no significant gender-based differences in PTSD symptoms were found. The study concludes with a detailed discussion on its practical implications, limitations, and recommendations for future research.

Keywords: Posttraumatic stress disorder, Motor vehicle survivors, orthopaedics trauma Patients.

INTRODUCTION

Road traffic accidents, also known as traffic collisions or car accidents, are incidents that occur when vehicles on the road collide with each other, pedestrians, animals, or objects. These accidents can result in property damage, injuries, and even fatalities. Road traffic accidents are a significant global concern and cause a considerable number of deaths and injuries every year (Fisa, et al., 2022). The majority of road accidents are caused by human error or negligence, such as distracted driving, speeding, drunk driving, reckless behavior, fatigue, and failure to follow traffic rules. Poorly designed or maintained roads, inadequate signage, lack of lighting, and improper road markings can contribute to accidents. Mechanical failures, such as brake

failure, tire blowouts, or faulty steering systems, can lead to accidents. Poorly maintained vehicles or the use of defective parts can also be contributing factors. Adverse weather conditions like rain, snow, fog, or ice can make roads slippery and reduce visibility, increasing the risk of accidents. Pedestrians and cyclists who do not follow traffic rules or fail to pay attention to their surroundings can also contribute to accidents (Wu, et al., 2022). Road accidents result in a significant number of fatalities and injuries worldwide. The severity of the injuries can vary, ranging from minor cuts and bruises to severe damage or lasting disabilities.

These accidents have notable economic consequences, including medical costs, vehicle repairs, insurance charges, decreased productivity, and legal proceedings. Accidents can have long-

lasting emotional and psychological effects on survivors, witnesses, and the families of those involved, leading to trauma, anxiety, and stress disorders. Promoting safe driving practices, including obeying traffic rules, avoiding distractions, and responsible alcohol consumption, through public campaigns and educational programs. Developing well-designed roads, proper signage, street lighting, and pedestrian-friendly infrastructure to enhance safety. Strict enforcement of traffic laws, including speed limits, seatbelt usage, and drunk driving regulations, to discourage dangerous behaviors. Encouraging the use of safety features in vehicles, such as seatbelts, airbags, anti-lock braking systems, and electronic stability control. Enhancing public transportation systems to provide safer alternatives, reducing the number of private vehicles on the road. It is essential to prioritize road safety and take proactive measures to prevent road traffic accidents, as they have a significant impact on individuals, communities, and societies as a whole (Shahsavari, et al., 2022).

Indeed, road traffic accidents have the potential to induce post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), a psychological condition that may manifest following the experience or observation of a distressing event. Although PTSD is commonly associated with situations such as combat, natural disasters, or physical assault, road traffic accidents can also be traumatizing and act as triggers for its development. The probability of developing PTSD tends to increase in proportion to the severity of the accident, particularly if it involves significant injuries or loss of life. Individuals who were directly involved in the accident, either as drivers or passengers, are more at risk of developing PTSD than witnesses or bystanders. If individuals perceive their lives or the lives of others to be in immediate danger during the accident, it can increase the risk of developing PTSD. People with a history of trauma, prior mental health conditions, or inadequate coping skills may be more susceptible to developing PTSD after a road traffic accident (Elvik, et al., 2022).

Common symptoms of PTSD after a road traffic accident are distressing flashbacks, nightmares, or recurrent thoughts about the accident. Avoiding reminders of the accident, such as driving or being in vehicles, and avoiding discussions or thoughts related to the incident. Feeling constantly on edge, easily startled, having difficulty sleeping, or

experiencing irritability or anger. Feeling guilty, blaming oneself or others for the accident, memory problems, loss of interest in activities, or experiencing a negative outlook on life (Yimer, et al., 2023).

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) is a psychological disorder that can arise following exposure to or witnessing a traumatic event. It is characterized by a variety of symptoms that endure over a prolonged duration and have a significant impact on an individual's ability to function and enjoy a satisfactory quality of life (Brewin, et al., 2000). The symptoms of PTSD can be classified into four distinct categories: Intrusive Symptoms: These encompass the presence of recurring and distressing memories, flashbacks, nightmares or intense psychological distress triggered by cues or triggers associated with the traumatic event. Avoidance Symptoms: These involve deliberate efforts to avoid thoughts, emotions, or reminders associated with the traumatic event. This may include avoiding specific places, activities, or individuals that evoke memories of the trauma. Negative Alterations in Mood and Cognition: This category involves persistent negative emotional states, feelings of detachment, a loss of interest in previously enjoyed activities, difficulties in recalling the traumatic event, negative self-perceptions or beliefs about oneself and the world, and distorted attributions of blame. Hyper arousal Symptoms: These encompass heightened physiological and emotional reactivity, such as difficulty concentrating, irritability, hyper vigilance, anger outbursts, and an exaggerated startle response, and sleep-related problems (DSM-5, 2013).

The development of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) can be influenced by multiple factors, which can interact with each other and impact an individual's susceptibility to the condition. The intensity, duration, and perceived level of threat in the traumatic event significantly contribute to the likelihood of developing PTSD. Traumatic events that involve physical harm, sexual violence, witnessing death or injury, or situations evoking intense fear, helplessness, or horror are more prone to lead to PTSD. Additionally, certain individual factors can increase vulnerability to PTSD, including a history of previous trauma or adverse life experiences, pre-existing mental health conditions (such as anxiety or depression), childhood adversity (such as abuse

or neglect), personality traits (such as neuroticism), and a family history of mental health disorders (Kessler et al., 1995).

Sufficient social support and a robust network of support can serve as factors that protect against the occurrence of PTSD. Establishing nurturing connections with family, friends, or members of the community who offer emotional support, understanding, and aid can assist individuals in managing traumatic experiences. Conversely, a dearth of social support or feelings of isolation can heighten the risk of developing PTSD. Sensations of helplessness or perceiving a lack of control during a traumatic event can contribute to the onset of PTSD. Individuals who believe they had no influence over the situation or were incapable of preventing or escaping the trauma may be more susceptible to experiencing symptoms of PTSD (Resick & Schnicke, 1992).

Biological factors can influence a person's response to trauma and susceptibility to PTSD. Changes in the stress response system, such as cortisol and other stress hormone imbalances, genetic predispositions, and changes in brain regions involved in emotion regulation and fear processing, may be among these reasons. Resilience and effective coping methods help guard against PTSD. Individuals with adaptive coping strategies, problem-solving skills, positive self-perceptions, and emotional regulation abilities are more likely to recover from stressful events without acquiring PTSD. While these characteristics can all contribute to the development of PTSD, not everyone who witnesses a traumatic event will acquire the illness. The interaction of these elements, as well as individual characteristics, might have an impact on the outcome. Early intervention, social support, and proper coping methods can all assist to lessen the impact of these factors and lower the likelihood of having PTSD (Watkins et al., 2018).

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) can be understood by considering various dimensions that encompass the range of symptoms and experiences associated with the disorder. These dimensions provide a framework for comprehending and evaluating how PTSD affects an individual's functioning. The Re-Experiencing dimension involves intrusive symptoms characterized by the involuntary and distressing reliving of the traumatic event. It encompasses symptoms like recurring and intrusive memories, distressing

dreams related to the trauma, flashbacks, and intense psychological distress and physiological reactions triggered by reminders of the trauma. The avoidance dimension of PTSD refers to individuals' efforts to evade stimuli associated with the traumatic event. This can involve avoiding thoughts, feelings, or discussions connected to the trauma, as well as avoiding people, places, or activities that may act as reminders of the traumatic experience (Bryant et al., 2011).

Negative alterations in cognition and mood encompass the enduring negative changes in an individual's thoughts, emotions, and beliefs that occur in the aftermath of a traumatic event. This category includes symptoms such as persistent negative emotional states (such as sadness, guilt, or shame), ongoing inability to experience positive emotions, distorted perceptions about oneself or the world (such as negative self-beliefs, negative views of others, or a pessimistic outlook on the future), and decreased interest or engagement in activities previously enjoyed. The heightened physiological and psychological responses that persistently occur following a stressful incident are referred to as hyper arousal. These symptoms may manifest as irritability, outbursts of anger, difficulties with concentration, hyper vigilance (continuously scanning the environment for potential threats), exaggerated startle responses, and disturbances in sleep patterns (Brewin et al., 2010). These dimensions provide a comprehensive framework for understanding the diverse range of symptoms and experiences associated with PTSD. It is important to note that individuals may vary in the prominence and severity of symptoms across these dimensions. The assessment and diagnosis of PTSD typically involve evaluating the presence and impact of symptoms within each of these dimensions, along with their duration and functional impairment. Treatment approaches for PTSD often target these dimensions to alleviate symptoms and improve overall well-being (Stein, et al., 2013).

It is possible for orthopedic patients, particularly those who have undergone traumatic events such as severe accidents or surgeries, to develop symptoms of trauma or distress that can resemble certain aspects of PTSD. This can include intrusive thoughts or memories of the event, avoidance of activities or situations related to the trauma, heightened arousal or anxiety, and changes in mood or cognition. It's essential to differentiate

between normal distress and PTSD. If orthopedic patients are experiencing significant psychological distress related to their condition or treatment, it is recommended that they seek professional help from a mental health provider or discuss their concerns with their healthcare team. A comprehensive evaluation is necessary to determine if a formal diagnosis of PTSD or another mental health condition is appropriate and to develop an appropriate treatment plan (Gasperi et al., 2021).

Rationale of the Study

The rationale for studying Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) among motor vehicle survivors and orthopedic trauma patients is based on the recognition of the significant psychological impact that traumatic events can have on individuals. Motor vehicle accidents and orthopedic trauma are common events that can result in physical injuries, pain, and emotional distress. Motor vehicle accidents and orthopedic trauma can be highly distressing events that have the potential to cause significant psychological trauma. Research has shown that a considerable proportion of survivors of these events may develop PTSD. Understanding the prevalence and impact of PTSD in these populations is essential for identifying those in need of appropriate interventions and support. Orthopedic trauma patients often experience significant physical injuries, which can lead to pain, functional limitations, and changes in their daily lives. The combination of physical and psychological distress can exacerbate the risk of developing PTSD. Studying PTSD among orthopedic trauma patients helps to explore the complex interplay between physical and psychological factors and their influence on recovery and overall well-being. Identifying PTSD symptoms among motor vehicle survivors and orthopedic trauma patients is crucial for effective treatment planning. PTSD can significantly impact the recovery process, adherence to treatment protocols, and overall rehabilitation outcomes. Recognizing and addressing PTSD symptoms alongside the physical injuries can lead to more comprehensive and targeted treatment approaches that address both the physical and psychological aspects of recovery.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the difference between motor vehicle survivors and orthopedics trauma patients in term of post-traumatic stress disorder
2. To study the difference between male and female in terms of post-traumatic stress disorder.

Hypotheses

- H1 There would be a difference between motor vehicle survivors and orthopedics trauma patients in term of post-traumatic stress disorder.
- H2 In terms of post-traumatic stress disorder, there would be a gender difference.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The sample was drawn using a straightforward sampling strategy based on a cross-sectional survey study design.

Sample of the Study

The current study's sample size of 200 (100 males and 100 female) was drawn from two hospitals (Nishtar Hospital Multan and DHQ Muzaffargarh).

Inclusion Criteria

- This study contained a sample of 200 people (100 men and 100 women).
- Age range for this study 20 to 30 was included.
- Motor vehicle survivors with minor injuries.

Exclusion Criteria

- The below the age of 20 and above the age of 30 was excluded in the study.
- Students who were not willing to participate were excluded.
- Orthopedic trauma patients with severe injuries.

Instruments

Demographic Form

To acquire the necessary information about each student, a demographical sheet or form was created. This form was used to conduct additional analysis on the result section.

Post-Traumatic Stress Scale

Post-traumatic stress scale by Edna B. Foa (2013) was used to examine post-traumatic stress. It consists of 24 items and uses a 5-point Likert scale (0 = Not at all to 4 = Extremely) to rate the frequency and severity of each symptom. The scale has alpha reliability of .89.

Procedure

Samples for this study were obtained from Nishtar Hospital Multan and DHQ Muzaffargarh. Prior to data collection, participants provided informal consent. Alongside the measurement scales, participants completed a demographic sheet. Ethical considerations, including informed consent, confidentiality, and project debriefing, were taken into account. Data was collected using the scales. Descriptive statistics and an independent sample t-test were performed for statistical analysis using SPSS23.

Statistical Analysis

To examine the overall distribution of the data, Descriptive Statistics was utilized. The statistical version SPSS 23 was used to perform an independent sample t-test statistical analysis to determine the statistical significant difference between these variables.

Ethical Consideration

To adhere to ethical requirements, participants provided their informed consent by signing a consent form. They were also provided with information about the study's objectives. The authors took additional measures to ensure the privacy and security of participants' data. In accordance with ethical guidelines, the use of questionnaires and other necessary considerations were approved.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter delves into the statistical analysis of the current study. The study's data was examined using statistical program for social science (SPSS), with a significance level of 0.01 applied for all analyses. To examine the overall distribution of the data, Descriptive Statistics was utilized. The statistical version SPSS 23 was used to perform an independent sample t-test statistical analysis to determine the statistical significant difference between these variables.

Table 4.1: Frequencies and Percentages of Demographic Variables of Study (N = 200)

Variables	Category	F	%
Gender	Male	100	50.00
	Female	100	50.00
Age	20-24	126	63.00
	25-30	74	37.00
Population	Motor Vehicle Survivor	100	50.00
	Orthopedics Trauma Patients	100	50.00
	Total	200	100.0

Note. F = Frequency, % = Percentage

The demographic features of the sample were shown in the table above. The age ranges and gender distributions are 100%. There were 100 males and 100 females in the sample of 200,

ranging in age from 20 to 30. There were 126 people aged 20-24 and 74 people aged 25-30. There were 100 survivors of motor vehicle accidents and 100 orthopedic trauma patients.

Table 4.2: Psychometric Properties of the Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder Scale (N=200)

Scales	SD	M	Range	α	Skewness	Kurtosis
Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder Scale	10.70	54.7	24-90	.58	.29	.64

Table 2 displays the mean standard deviation, kurtosis, skewness, and Scale dependability. Descriptive statistics are employed to examine the overall distribution of data across research variables. The mean of the post-traumatic stress

disorder scale is 54.7, and the standard deviation is 10.70, indicating that the data is normally distributed and meets the parametric testing assumption. The scale's Cronbach's Alpha value is .58.

Table 4.3: Mean Difference between Motor Vehicle Survivor and Orthopaedics Trauma Patients In Terms of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder

	MVS (n=100)		OTP (n=100)		t	p	95% CI	
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL
Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder	55.29	10.5	54.20	10.8	.719	.473	-1.89	4.07

Note. LL = Lower limit, UL = Upper limit

The mean score for individuals who survived motor vehicle accidents is 55.29, while the mean score for orthopedic trauma patients is 54.20. The calculated t -value is 0.719, and the corresponding p -value is 0.473. Since the p -value is higher than the commonly used alpha level, there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis assumes that there is no significant

difference between the means of the two groups. Therefore, there is no statistically significant difference in post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) between motor vehicle accident survivors and orthopedic trauma patients. This suggests that the average PTSD scores of the two groups are quite similar.

Table 4.4: Mean Difference between male and Female (Motor Vehicle Survivor and Orthopaedics Trauma Patients) in Terms of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder

	Male (n=100)		Female (n=100)		t	p	95% CI	
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL
Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder	54.30	11.2	55.19	10.1	-.587	.821	-3.88	2.10

Note. LL = Lower limit, UL = Upper limit

In t -value, the negative sign (-0.787) indicates that the mean score for males is lower than the mean score for females. The p -value of 0.558 suggests that the observed difference in mean scores between males and females is not statistically significant. Based on results, we can interpret that there is no significant difference in post-traumatic stress disorder scores between males and females. The small mean difference and the high p -value indicate that any observed differences are likely due to random chance rather than a true difference in population means.

Discussion

The current study looked at the differences in post-traumatic stress disorder between motor vehicle survivors and orthopedic trauma patients. The study also looked at the differences in post-traumatic stress disorder between men and women. The current study's sample of 200 people (100 men and 100 women) was drawn from Nishtar Hospital Multan and DHQ Muzaffargarh. The Post-Traumatic Stress Scale was employed in the study. SPSS was used to analyse the data from the Cross Sectional Research Design.

The current chapter, "Discussion of this study," will thoroughly explore the findings and contributing

factors. The analysis of the results will elucidate the primary causes that underlie these significant discoveries, taking into account previous research. The discussion will focus on the factors and elements that act as underlying contributors, increasing the vulnerability of students to various psychological and emotional issues. Additionally, the role of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) in the development of these problems among motor vehicle survivors and orthopedic trauma patients will be examined. The scientific literature has effectively articulated several influential components that significantly impact PTSD among these groups. Understanding these crucial factors would assist in enhancing our understanding of the findings from our empathetic study, which examines the prevalence of PTSD among motor vehicle survivors and orthopedic trauma patients in Pakistan. The discussion will delve into the potential origins and underlying determinants that contribute to the subjective well-being of adolescents. While the primary focus of the current research was on the prevalence of PTSD among motor vehicle survivors and orthopedic trauma patients, exploring these related factors will provide valuable insights.

Hypothesis 1

“There would be a difference between motor vehicle survivors and orthopedics trauma patients in term of post-traumatic stress disorder”.

The initial hypothesis of the study proposed that there would be a distinction in post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) between individuals who survived motor vehicle accidents and those who experienced orthopedic trauma. However, the results obtained from the independent sample *t*-test presented in table 3 indicate that there is no significant disparity in PTSD between these two groups. Therefore, there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, which assumes that there is no significant difference in the mean levels of PTSD between motor vehicle survivors and orthopedic trauma patients. In conclusion, the study's findings suggest that there is no statistically significant distinction in the prevalence of post-traumatic stress disorder between these two populations. This means that the two groups do not significantly differ in terms of their mean PTSD scores. Previous research also showed that both motor vehicle survivors and orthopedic trauma patients can be at risk for developing PTSD, but the prevalence and severity also same. Motor vehicle accidents can be highly traumatic events, often involving life-threatening situations, which can contribute to a higher risk of PTSD with same intensity as orthopedic trauma patients (Gabbet al., 2016).

When it is said that there is no difference in post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) symptoms or diagnoses between motor vehicle survivors and orthopedic trauma patients, it means that both groups have comparable rates or intensities of PTSD symptoms or diagnoses. The specific research or study that compared these two groups found no statistically significant difference in the presence or severity of PTSD symptoms. This research implies that being involved in a car accident or suffering orthopedic trauma does not significantly increase the risk or chance of getting PTSD. Both groups may have similar levels of discomfort, intrusive thoughts, avoidance behaviors, and other PTSD symptoms. It is critical to recognize that this result is unique to the study or research being cited. Other studies or research endeavors may have different results, so it is important to study a variety of studies to acquire a thorough picture of the association between trauma type and the development of PTSD (Wilker et al., 2021).

Hypothesis 2

“There would be a difference between motor vehicle survivors and orthopedics trauma patients in term of post-traumatic stress disorder”.

The study's second hypothesis posited that there would be a divergence in post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) between males and females. However, the outcomes of the independent sample *t*-test presented in table 4 indicate that there is no significant variance in PTSD between men and women. Thus, there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, which assumes that there is no substantial distinction in the mean levels of PTSD between the two genders. Consequently, there is no statistically significant distinction between men and women in terms of post-traumatic stress disorder. These findings suggest that the average PTSD scores of the two groups are fairly similar. The previous study conducted by Kessler et al. (1995) investigated the occurrence and sociodemographic factors associated with post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) in the National Comorbidity Survey. Their findings align with the notion that there is no disparity between genders when it comes to PTSD. Similarly, in a separate article authored by Tolin and Foa (2006), a quantitative review encompassing a 25-year research period was conducted to explore sex differences in trauma exposure and PTSD. The review encompassed a diverse range of studies and aimed to evaluate potential variations in prevalence, symptomatology, risk factors, and treatment outcomes related to PTSD based on gender. The authors presented an extensive synthesis of existing literature on gender differences in trauma and PTSD, highlighting significant findings that indicate the absence of a significant gender discrepancy in relation to PTSD.

The previous scholarly article presents an extensive and systematic review that encompasses 25 years of research focused on investigating sex differences in trauma exposure and the development of posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD). The authors meticulously examine and synthesize the outcomes from diverse studies to offer a comprehensive overview of gender disparities in the prevalence, symptoms, risk factors, and treatment outcomes associated with PTSD. The review elucidates the variations in traumatic experiences and the manifestation of PTSD symptoms between males and females, shedding light on the potential influence of gender on the onset and expression of PTSD. This review significantly contributes to the existing body of

knowledge on sex differences in trauma and PTSD and provides valuable insights for future research and clinical applications in this field (Iribarren , et al., 2005).

When it is stated that there is no significant difference between males and females concerning post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), it indicates that the observed variations in PTSD symptoms or diagnoses between the two genders lack statistical significance. In other words, the differences or discrepancies observed between males and females in relation to PTSD are not deemed substantial or meaningful based on the statistical analysis conducted in the referenced study or research. This finding suggests that, within the specific study or research being discussed, there is no noteworthy distinction between males and females regarding their vulnerability to or experience of PTSD symptoms subsequent to a traumatic event. Both genders may exhibit comparable rates or levels of PTSD symptoms, indicating that gender does not play a significant role in the development or manifestation of PTSD. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that this conclusion is drawn from the specific study or research being referenced. Other studies or research endeavors may yield differing results, and it is always valuable to consider a range of studies to establish a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between gender and PTSD. Additionally, it is essential to recognize that gender is merely one factor among many that may influence the experience and manifestation of PTSD (Miao ., 2018).

SUMMARY, FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

The current study looked at the differences in post-traumatic stress disorder between motor vehicle survivors and orthopaedic trauma patients. The study also looked at the differences in post-traumatic stress disorder between men and women. The current study's sample of 200 people (100 men and 100 women) was drawn from Nishtar Hospital Multan and DHQ Muzaffargarh. The Post-Traumatic Stress Scale was employed in the study. SPSS was used to examine the data from the Cross-Sectional Research Design. The findings demonstrated that there is no significant difference in post-traumatic stress disorder between motor vehicle survivors and orthopaedic trauma patients. The findings also found that there is no substantial

difference in post-traumatic stress disorder between men and women.

Recommendations

The sample for this study was obtained from Nishtar Hospital Multan and DHQ Muzaffargarh. To enhance the study's robustness, it is suggested that future research should consider selecting samples from a broader range of hospitals in different locations. While the current study employed a cross-sectional design, it is recommended that future studies adopt a longitudinal approach to examine post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) among motor vehicle survivors and orthopedic trauma patients. This would yield more comprehensive data, enhance the study's comparability, and increase its effectiveness. One limitation of the current study is its reliance solely on self-reported data, which may introduce biases. To overcome this, future studies could incorporate interviews to obtain a more thorough and detailed understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, it is important to note that the current study employed convenient sampling, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Random sampling methods should be utilized in future studies to ensure a fair and accurate representation of the population.

To further advance research efforts, several recommendations are proposed based on the implications outlined below. Firstly, there is a need for additional research to elucidate contextual factors. The study's findings can be applied to both public and private hospitals in Pakistan as well as other countries. To enhance the generalizability of the findings, data collection from a wider range of hospitals should be considered. Employing random sampling techniques would facilitate the accurate representation of the population. Future studies would benefit from including samples with diverse age groups and demographic characteristics to ensure broader applicability of the findings.

Limitations

The sample for the current study was obtained from Nishtar Hospital Multan and DHQ Muzaffargarh, which may not accurately represent all motor vehicle survivors and orthopedic trauma patients. In future studies, it would be advisable to include samples from additional hospitals in different cities to ensure a more comprehensive representation.

The current study utilized a cross-sectional research design, but it is recommended that future research adopt a longitudinal approach to further investigate this topic. Conducting a longitudinal study would allow for the collection of more detailed and comprehensive data, as well as enhance comparability within the study. Another limitation of the current study is the exclusive use of self-reported information for analysis, which can introduce biases.

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